

STUDYING ABDULLA AVLANI'S WORKS "VATANNI SUYMAK" AND "VATAN" IN A PROBLEM-BASED METHOD

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INTRODUCTION

Today, Uzbekistan is entering a new, high stage of its development. We have made it our most important and priority task to achieve national revival - national rise. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "This great goal can be achieved only by living in harmony with the people of the world, building an open democratic society, and establishing a greater sense of respect for national and universal values in our lives."

From this point of view, it is necessary to study and promote Uzbek classic literature on an international level, to analyze this multi-faceted topic in connection with the most important processes taking place in the world literary environment today. Remarkable works being carried out in Uzbekistan, in particular, tasks such as consistent development of science, education, culture, art and literature, increasing reading culture, have become the priority of state policy. Because President Shavkat We understand that the words of Mirziyoyev, "Development of literature and art, culture are a solid foundation for raising the spiritual world of our people." Also, the adoption of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of a special fund for the support of spirituality and creativity" is an improvement of the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in our country, which our people have respected for centuries. It was the next important step in the ongoing systematic activities to preserve national values and traditions, support intellectuals, first of all, people of words, and create favorable conditions for their effective creativity.

On August 3, 2017, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting with creative intellectuals of our country. At this meeting, attention was paid to many problems that have arisen in the field of literature and art. At this meeting, culture, mass media, the works carried out in order to fundamentally reform the sphere of literature and art were discussed, new ideas, initiatives and proposals were presented for the purpose of education of young talents, development of our culture and literature: There is one very important issue that I think needs to be addressed, and it is related to the upbringing of our young generation, our children. As our great grandfather Abdulla Avloni said, this issue is really a matter of life, death, salvation, destruction, happiness, or disaster for us. The rich pedagogical heritage of the writer, which is closely connected with the mentality, lifestyle, and national values, served as a national school and a valuable resource for developing educational issues, forming it in the hearts of students, and raising morally and spiritually mature young people. research is becoming the demand of the times.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Information about the life and work of Abdulla Avloni is included in the 5th grade school textbook. 1 hour for his life and work, reading and analyzing the stories "True Friend" and

"False Friend" 1 hour, 1 hour is allocated for reading the stories "The wolf with Khurus" and "Harm of strife". There is no separate hour for the works "Vatanni suymak" and "Vatan". A. Avloni describes his sincere thoughts to children in playful lines, as well as serious comments about the Motherland and its fate.

If you read the chapter "Loving the Motherland", fully feeling the period when this work was written - the time when our country was in a tragic situation under the influence of colonialism, trampled under the feet of foreigners, it is said that a person should sacrifice even his life for the independence and freedom of the country. It is not difficult to feel that it is embedded in the layers of the work. The soil of the homeland is sacred: there are the rights of our ancestors in it, and the rights of our future generations are in it. That is why it is not possible to simply love the Motherland, it is also important to mourn, fight for its future, and hand it over to future generations in full prosperity.

love your country. You have to live with his pain, rejoice in his happiness, be proud of him. Motherland is as sacred as Motherland. It is the child's duty to appreciate and respect him, to be a part of his happiness and joy, to share his sadness. This is how Avloni understands the Motherland and the duty before it.

Children are also different. There are also children who share their mother's happiness and leave her alone when she is unhappy. There are not many children who admire the beautiful nature and gardens of the country, but do not think about their worries and sorrows. One should love the country, no matter what it is.

"North, the coldest snow and ice lands more than any other place. If they didn't like it, they would have left their homeland and emigrated to places with good air and easy life. Our grandfathers used to say, "Be a shepherd in your own country until there is a sultan in another's country."

The author tries to justify his opinion with various examples. For example, he gives this parable. Some people sell their yards and property and go on pilgrimage to Mecca. Even most of them return to their homeland. "The reason for this, that is, the force that pulls them together, is the love of the soil of their homeland..." he says.

The scope of love is wide. Love for the country, love for the people, love for a friend, love for the country... But one thing is very clear in its meaning. Love is a longing for someone, something. Burning with the feeling of considering him as his soul, giving his whole existence to him. A great desire to make him happy and joyful. He can turn the desert into a bosom, he can make a flower out of a stone. Avloni begins the chapter called "Love" with the following lines: '

It is said to love something. People in the world live in the shadow of love and kindness. They do everything out of love. People without love cannot have the courage and enthusiasm to do any work, they cannot enjoy the blessings of the world. If a student does not love knowledge and the teacher, if he does not study with appetite, he will not reach his goal. The thing that brings people on earth to wars and fights, and makes them aim their chests at the enemy's arrows, is the love of their religions and nations, motherland and states. Isn't it the love of the motherland and children that makes a person toil day and night like a slave and work hard?!" pedagogical thought at the beginning of the 20th century. In it, the issues of education and morality were analyzed for the first time from the perspective of the demands and needs of the 20th century. Avloni divides the traditional good and bad behaviors and takes modernity as the main criterion, proving his opinions with the opinions of Hippocrates, Plato, Aristotle,

Saadi Shirozi, Bedil. Adib considered the love of the country to fight for it as one of the best human qualities.

"Homeland. The city and country where a person was born is called his homeland. Everyone loves the place where he was born and grew up more than his life. The poet calls on the people, especially the young people, to appreciate, love, rejuvenate and care for the Motherland. This is what he understood by the Motherland and love for it.

Abdulla Avloni wrote a number of poems and parables for children. In these works, the poet aims to expand the scope of thinking of school-age children, to instill in them love for school and books, work, nature, and the Motherland. Many of his poems are based on the idea of loving the Motherland. In these poems, the poet described the Motherland in simple and sincere verses, which not only those of the middle of the 10s, but also today's school-age children can get great aesthetic pleasure from them.

In fact, the poet begins the description of the Motherland, "Mines are extracted from its mountains, grains are extracted from its lands... It is a very pleasant air, It is rocky and sandy with deserts, It is not Tashkent, it is melting stone, Its cuts are melting flower", - says the mother to the children. achieves great love for the country.

each person was born and grew up is called the homeland of that person. Everyone loves his place of birth and upbringing more than his life. Even animals have this sense of homeland. If an animal loses its homeland, it will not live as comfortably as it did in its own land..." says Avloni.

Abdulla Awlani, like the thinkers of the past, calls on young people to love the Motherland. Adib hates those chasing after wealth, seeing that they are engaged in things that do not correspond to humaneness. Avloni urges young people not to focus on wealth. Makes wealth look like a fleeting cloud. Adib explains in a simple and impressive way the meaning of the concept of the Motherland, the value of the country where he was born and raised for a person in the work "Love the Motherland".

Adib describes the feeling of the Motherland as one of the most human and honorable feelings. You can't just love your country. You have to live with his pain, rejoice in his happiness, be proud of him.

Avloni substantiates his opinion about the Motherland with various examples. For example, some people sell their houses and go to Mecca. But most of them return to their homeland. Adib explains the reason for the yearning for the Motherland as follows: "The reason for this, that is, the strength that drives them, is the love of their homeland, their soil..." At the end of the video, our Prophet says: He quotes his holy words: "Loving the country is a matter of faith".

Abdulla Avloni continues his thoughts about the Motherland in his poems published in 1916 in the book "School Gulistani". The poem "Motherland" in this book is especially noteworthy. This work can be called a hymn to the honor of the Motherland. It begins with the following fiery lines:

Your name is holy in this world,
Everyone doesn't know your worth - they have a low mind...
You are our mother! You are our wonderful mother!
You are our living room!

In this poem, a beautiful and glorious landscape of the motherland is drawn. His feeling fills hearts with pride and relieves pain. Not loving him, not respecting him, not appreciating him will destroy a person.

In "Word of Hijran" a beautiful, rich and glorious landscape of the motherland is drawn.

Therefore, it is necessary to sacrifice lives for him:

If my soul dies from my body because it is my country, my country,

There will be no sorrow, I think of my generation and my country.

My body is full of dust, my body is full of fear,

Charoki, my homeland is my grave

The place where I grew up, this Motherland is my body

If he dies, it will be really sad'

In his poem "Motherland", he tries to describe the blessings of the motherland, its unique wealth. The artist compares the Motherland to a mother. Through his work, he puts forward the idea that only a child who respects and protects his mother can protect his country from evil forces.

You are our mother! You are our wonderful mother!

You are our living room!

Think for yourself if you can be sold

If you have a language, tell me about your wishes

We buy and sell, drowning in sadness,

Lying in the rubble like an owl.

ruined, and that only enlightened souls can save the country from such a calamity.

A separate hour is not allocated for these passages presented in the 5th grade literature textbook. This should be explained to the students while introducing the topic of Avloni's life and work to the students, drawing a didactic analysis. When teaching students in the literature class, it is necessary to approach based on the following interpretation: "What is the example of Abdullah Awlani's life and work, what does the writer call us to do in the film "Love the Motherland", the meaning of the hadith "Love the Motherland is from faith" attempt to interpret". Because this interpretation is determined based on the general goal of literary education.

Any work that is interpreted to students for learning in literature classes will be less effective if it is not subjected to didactic analysis, if it is not included in its content, and if it is not discussed among students. It is important not only to teach them to the students, but also to explain the essence of the topic, to introduce a problem question and a problem task to explain the topic. For example:

Problem: How did you understand the saying "Be a shepherd in your own country until there is a sultan in your own country" mentioned in the work?

Logical questions and tasks that guide the student to the solution of the problem:

1. Who do you mean by Sultan and what does he do?
2. Who is the shepherd and what does he do?
3. Which one would you choose?
4. How did you understand the summary?

Problem: Who is Rasuli akram nabiyi muhtaram sallallahu alayhi wasallam, mentioned in the work?

Logical questions and tasks that guide the student to the solution of the problem:

1. Who is Rasuli Akram and what have you heard about him?
 2. How do you understand the meaning of the word Nabi?
 3. Have you heard about the meaning of the combination of peace and blessings be upon you?
- Problem: How do you interpret the meaning of the hadith "To love one's country is from faith"?

Logical questions and tasks that guide the student to the solution of the problem:

1. What do you mean by homeland?
2. What emotions do you feel when you say love for the country, love for the country?
3. How do you understand the word faith? Try to explain the meaning.
4. What is a hadith?
5. What other wise words, hadiths, proverbs have you heard about the country?

In the course of the lesson, teaching the work to the students and organizing a discussion on the questions presented above regarding the content of the text of the work. considered appropriate. Each student in the class thinks about the problem within his capacity and gives his opinion. Under the guidance of the teacher, these thoughts are summarized and a solution to the problem is found.

The programmatic interpretation of the poem "Motherland" presented in the 5th grade textbook is as follows: "Motherland" poem is a hymn to the Motherland, a poetic expression of the beautiful and glorious scenery of the Motherland.

"It takes four to five minutes to read Vatan's poem expressively. The teacher should read this poem himself. Because the content of the poem imposes a tone on its reading. The teacher arouses the student's interest by reading it expressively. After the reading, a didactic analysis of the text of the work will be conducted with the help of questions and assignments.

In the first step, it is important to create an understanding of the sense of the Motherland among students. Then, problematic questions are raised that encourage the reader to think and observe about the work.

1. Why do you think the name of the Motherland is sacred in this world?
2. In the poem, why does the poet say that those who do not know the value of the Motherland are of low intelligence called?
 3. Why does the poet call the Motherland our mother in the poem?
 4. What does the poet mean by "treasure in your chest"?
 5. Why did the poet compare the sad to an owl?
 6. In the poem, what kind of catastrophes does the punishment of lack of education and ignorance lead to?
 7. How do you understand the expression "flood of grief" in the poem?
 8. What do you think the poet means by using the nickname "Hijran" at the end of the poem?

While working on such questions and tasks, students try to express in words the feeling of love for the Motherland, this feeling that is characteristic of a person.

idea of spiritual and educational education. Also, the fact that Abdulla Avloni was embodied as a perfect creator of the first textbooks with his creative heritage, the concepts of education, love of the Motherland, freedom in his works, the research of ideological and artistic observations, the relevance of the subject is evident in the work of the enlightened writer, prolific creator, Avloni, who reveals the most important issue of today - education and

upbringing in the examples of stories and poetic pictures. It would not be wrong to say that the practical work of this great writer is a lesson for our youth today.

